

A mild and efficient semi-synthesis of shikonin leucoacetates

Wen Zhou, De-Feng Xu, Ai-Hong Zhao and Shao-Shun Li*

School of Pharmacy, Shanghai Jiaotong University, Minhang, Shanghai 200240, P. R. China

E-mail : sslis@sjtu.edu.cn Fax : 86-21-34204775

Manuscript received 20 April 2007, revised 21 August 2007, accepted 28 September 2007

Abstract : A mild and efficient synthesis of shikonin triacetate is developed by acetylation of shikonin with anhydrous acetic anhydride in the presence of iodine as an extremely powerful catalyst under solvent-free condition in 94.5% yield, then a regioselective reduction of carbonyl of 1,4-naphthoquinone with sodium monoacetoxyborohydride and acetylation of shikonin triacetate can afford shikonin leucoacetates with the yield of 76.4%.

Keywords : Shikonin leucoacetates, shikonin triacetate, acetylation, monoacetoxyborohydride.

Introduction

Shikonin leucoacetates has a significant marketing advantage of being a colorless compound, rather than a brightly colored pigment¹. It was shown to have improved pharmacological properties relative to shikonin². It was also orally active against carrageenan induced hind paw edema, and exhibited a tendency to heal gastric ulcers induced by acetic acid³. It was shown to be more active than acetylshikonin with respect to acceleration of granuloma formation⁴. It showed strong inhibition when applied topically against delayed-type allergies (ear edema) induced by oxazolone and dinitrofluorobenzene⁵. However, only the synthesis of shikonin leucoacetates has been reported with the yield of 21.6% in the literature⁶. The method is of rather hard, complicated work-up and, therefore, impractical. In the paper, we have reported a mild and efficient synthesis of shikonin leucoacetates utilizing iodine, monoacetoxyborohydride, acetic anhydride, diisopropylethylamine from shikonin in three steps.

Results and discussion

The quinone may be selectively reduced with Zn¹ or Na₂S₂O₄⁷ to provide a high air-selectively tetrahydroxynaphthalene derivative, which has been trapped as pentaacetyl derivation⁸. However, treatment of shikonin with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate in the presence of zinc dust gave many blue fluorescence products at 50~60 °C, because shikonin is susceptible to photooxidation by exposure to air or heat⁹. Furthermore, shikonin is readily polymerized in the presence of acids, base, heat, or light¹⁰. So we optimized the synthetic conditions of shikonin leucoacetates according to the reported

literature together with the above mentioned factors.

We adopted a mild reaction conditions to prepare for shikonin leucoacetate in three steps. First shikonin triacetate could be developed by acetylation of shikonin with anhydrous acetic anhydride in the presence of iodine as an extremely powerful catalyst under solvent-free condition at 0~5 °C in 94.5% yield. Interestingly, the ratio (1 : 10) of iodine to shikonin had been found to be the most satisfactory. Then the regioselective reduction of shikonin triacetate with sodium mono-acetoxyborohydride, which was generated by addition of the requisite amount of glacial acetic acid to a suspension of sodium borohydride in dry THF, followed by acetylation of the resulting phenols with anhydrous acetic anhydride and ⁱ-Pr₂EtN at room temperature, furnished shikonin leucoacetates with the yield of 76.4% (Scheme 1). Compared to the first step, I₂ couldn't be used to accelerate the acetylation of **3**, which could be easily oxidized by I₂ or O₂ back to shikonin triacetate.

In general, sodium monoacetoxyborohydride proves to be an attractive alternative to existing highly regioselective reagent during the course of preparation of shikonin leucoacetates. On the other hand, iodine shows very strong catalytic activity for acetylation of shikonin when the reaction is carried out without adding solvent. The current contribution also describes the use of diisopropylethylamine as efficient base for the acetylation reaction of 1,4-dihydroxy shikonin triacetate. The present method shows a very promising synthetic process for the shikonin leucoacetates because of the following advantages : (i) very high yield, (ii) simplicity of process, (iii) decreasing the by-products, (iv) the mild reac-

tion conditions and (v) that the protocol reported in this paper can be easily developed into large-scale preparation of the shikonin leucoacetates.

Scheme 1. (a) Ac_2O , I_2 ; (b) $\text{NaBH}_3(\text{OAc})$; (c) ${}^i\text{Pr}_2\text{EtN}$, Ac_2O .

Experimental

General :

Reagents and solvents were obtained from commercial supplier and were applied according to Reference⁷. All melting points were determined on SGW_B X-4 micro-melting point apparatus and were uncorrected. IR spectra were run on a NICOLET IMPACT-400 spectrometer. NMR spectra were recorded on Varian Mercury-300 spectrometer (300 MHz for ${}^1\text{H}$ and 100 MHz for ${}^{13}\text{C}$), chemical shifts of ${}^1\text{H}$ and ${}^{13}\text{C}$ were recorded in parts per million relative to the solvent resonance as internal standard (CDCl_3 , $\delta = 7.26, 77.36$ ppm; $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$, $\delta = 2.05, 30.92, 207.07$ ppm). Splitting patterns were designated as s, singlet; d, doublet; t, triplet; q, quartlet; m, multiplet. Mass spectra were obtained on a ZAB-2F spectrometer. TLC was carried out on silica gel (GF₂₅₄). Column chromatography was run on silica gel (200 ~ 300 mesh) from Qingdao Ocean Chemical Co. Ltd.

Shikonin (1) : 100 g of root powders of *Lithospermum erythrorhizon* grown in Liao-lin Province (P.C.R.) were extracted with hexane by Soxhlet apparatus. After solvent evaporation, the preliminary extract was dissolved in 20 ml methanol. The mixture was centrifuged (4200 r/min) at room temperature, then the upper layer was decanted to the solution of cupric acetate. The copper ion of hydroxynaphthoquinones complex was displaced by 4% hydrochloric acid for several hours. Following filtrate, the residue containing shikonin and its derivatives was hydrolyzed with NaOH (1 L, 1 N) and stirred at room temperature overnight. The aqueous phase of the aliquots was adjusted to pH 3 with concentrated HCl producing shikonin. Filtration and drying in vacuum desiccator

gave red-brownish needles. m.p. 148–149 °C (lit. 146–147 °C¹⁰). ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ (ppm) : 12.59 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 12.49 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 7.19 (2H, d, J 1.83 Hz, Ar-H), 7.17 (1H, s, H_{Quin}), 5.20 (1H, dd, J 8.01, 5.10 Hz, =CH-), 4.91 (1H, t, J 7.20 Hz, -OCH-), 2.62 ~ 2.66 (1H, m, - CH_2 -), 2.31 ~ 2.38 (1H, m, - CH_2 -), 1.76 (3H, s, - CH_3), 1.65 (3H, s, - CH_3); ${}^{13}\text{C}$ NMR (CDCl_3) : δ (ppm) : 180.6, 180.1, 165.7, 165.1, 151.5, 137.7, 132.5, 132.3, 132.0, 118.6, 112.3, 111.7, 68.6, 35.1, 25.2, 18.3; EI-MS : m/z 288.2 [M^+], 287.4 [$\text{M}^+ - 1$].

Shikonin triacetate (2) : A mixture of shikonin (100 mg, 0.35 mmol) and iodine (8.89 mg, 0.035 mL) in 1 ml anhydrous acetic anhydride was stirred for 2 h at 0 ~ 5 °C. Then acetic ether (8 ml) was added. 10 min later the organic phase was washed in turn with saturated sodium thiosulfate solution (5 ml), water (3 × 5 ml) and saturated brine (5 ml) followed by drying over anhydrous MgSO_4 and evaporation to give the crude product. Further purification with chromatography on silica gel (PE : EtOAc = 5 : 1) gave **2** as saffron yellow solid (127.94 mg) in 94.5% yields. m.p. 102–104.5 °C. (lit. m.p. 102–104 °C¹¹). ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR (CDCl_3) : δ (ppm) : 7.38 (2H, d, J 1.20 Hz, Ar-H), 6.66 (1H, s, H_{Quin}), 5.87 (1H, dd, J 3.33 Hz, =CH-), 5.07 (1H, dd, J 7.83, 1.26 Hz, -OCH-), 2.38 (6H, s, Ar-OCO- CH_3), 2.18 (3H, s, O-CO- CH_3), 2.32 ~ 2.44 (2H, m, - CH_2 -), 1.75 (3H, s, - CH_3), 1.65 (3H, s, - CH_3).

1,4-Dihydroxylshikonin triacetate (3) : A solution of **2** (100 mg, 0.242 mmol) in 3 ml THF was added to a mixture of acetic acid (27.66 μml , 0.484 mmol) and sodium borohydride (19.36 mg, 0.484 mmol). The mixture was stirred vigorously at room temperature for approximately 2 h (disappearance of the orange color of solution). TLC analysis indicated the reaction to be complete. The mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure to afford crude **3** which was used in the next step without further purification to avoid oxidation by exposure to air.

Shikonin leucoacetates (4) : The crude compound **3** was dissolved in the mixture of anhydrous acetic anhydride (2 ml) and ${}^i\text{Pr}_2\text{EtN}$ (1 ml); the mixture was stirred at room temperature. The reaction was monitored by TLC. After the completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was decanted to acetic ether (10 ml), then washed with water (3 × 10 ml), brine (10 ml) followed by drying over MgSO_4 . The crude product gained upon removal of acetic ether by evaporation showed one spot on TLC. Further purification with chromatography on silica gel (PE : EtOAc = 3 : 1) gave **4** (91.42 mg) as colorless

solid, m.p. 156.5–160 °C (lit. m.p. 157–160 °C¹²). IR : 1760, 1730, 1660, 1370, 1240, 1190, 1176, 1125, 1040, 1014, 925, 907, 891, 887 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR ((CD₃)₂CO) : δ 7.40 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.31 (2H, s, Ar-H), 5.63 (1H, dd, *J* 7.26, 5.13 Hz, =CH-), 5.09 (1H, t, *J* 7.56 Hz, -OCH-), 2.65 ~ 2.53 (2H, m, -CH₂-), 2.49, 2.43, 2.42, 2.41 (3H, each s, Ar-OCO-CH₃), 2.02 (3H, s, O-CO-CH₃), 1.65 (3H, s, -CH₃), 1.56 (3H, s, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR ((CD₃)₂CO) : δ (ppm) : 169.1, 168.3, 168.2, 143.0, 142.9, 142.8, 135.2, 130.5, 123.1, 122.2, 120.8, 120.4, 117.2, 76.8, 25.0, 21.5, 21.4, 21.3, 21.2, 20.5, 20.3, 17.1.

Acknowledgement

The project is supported by Shanghai-SK research and development Foundation (2003014h).

References

1. V. P. Papageorgiou, A. N. Assimopoulou and E. A. Couladouros, *Angew. Chem Int. Ed.*, 1999, **38**, 270.
2. M. Hayashi, *Nippon Yakurigaku Zasshi*, 1977, **73**, 177.
3. M. Hayashi, *Nippon Yakurigaku Zasshi*, 1977, **73**, 197.
4. M. Hayashi, *Nippon Yakurigaku Zasshi*, 1977, **73**, 207.
5. P. Martin, *Science*, 1997, **276**, 76.
6. S. Ushio, O. Hideaki and K. Yoshitomo, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1981, **29**, 120.
7. F. Radt, "Elsevier's Encyclopaedia of Organic Chemistry", Elsevier Publishing Co. Inc., New York, 1954, Series III, Vol. 12B, p. 3184.
8. Y. Seto, S. Motoyoshi, H. Nakamura, T. Ishitoku and S. Isayama, *Yakurigaku Zasshi*, 1992, **112**, 260.
9. F. A. Chen, A. B. Wu and H. C. Hsu, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1996, **44**, 250.
10. V. P. Papageorgiou, *Chem. Chron.*, 1978, **7**, 46.
11. A. I. Birch and K. A. M. Walker *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1967, **15**, 3457.
12. S. Ushio, E. Yutaka, M. Terutaka and I. Yasuo, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1977, **25**, 2394.